

Enabling WIDER UPTAKE of water-smart solutions

Figure 1 Integrated management for circular economy based on water resources.

WIDER UPTAKE Policy brief #1:

BROADENING THE SCOPE IN WATER MANAGEMENT

The global water challenges are unprecedented. Water scarcity is already severe in many parts of the world. While scarcity of phosphorous and other resources is impending, more than 80 per cent of the world's wastewater is discharged without treatment. Radical change, towards a more sustainable water-smart society, is therefore required.¹

Circular economy provides opportunities for value creation from resource recovery and reuse of treated wastewater, contributing to economic, social, and environmental sustainability. However, it also involves several challenges. Some of these are technological, but many are mainly governance related. This brief, targeted to water managers and policy makers, provides five learnings on the kinds of change we need to transition towards water management systems suited for circular economy.

The principles of reduction, reclamation, reuse, recycling, and resource recovery are to some degree employed already. However, to realise the full potential for water-smart solutions, policymaking must address the interaction between technological and social processes and facilitate coupling of resource flows between sectors, as illustrated in Figure 1.

¹ Water Europe Vision (2020). <https://watereurope.eu/publications/>

Transitioning towards a water-smart society requires rethinking and development of new value chains. Industrial symbiosis, where traditionally separate industries generate value through increased physical exchange of materials, energy, water, and by-products, is core. To achieve this, water utilities, technology providers and actors in related sectors need to develop their industrial networks, in terms of,

- a. Interaction with policymakers, knowledge actors and the public to build awareness and acceptance.
- b. Development of new business models enabling valorisation of the recovered resources.
- c. Identification of specific partners and development of joint systems and procedures for optimal resource utilization.

WIDER UPTAKE, funded by the European Union, demonstrates a set of water-smart circular economy solutions in five countries:

- ✓ Reuse of treated wastewater for irrigation in public parks and agriculture (Italy, Czech Republic, Ghana)
- ✓ Fertilisers from sewage sludge and recovered phosphorous (Norway, Italy)
- ✓ Soil improvement from sewage sludge and other waste streams (Norway)
- ✓ Biogas from sewage sludge and other waste streams (Norway)
- ✓ Biochar from sewage sludge (Ghana)
- ✓ Material for bioplastics from sewage (Italy)
- ✓ Biocomposite production utilising calcite and cellulose from water and wastewater treatment (Netherlands)

Together, seven research partners and eleven industry partners will develop a roadmap for how to upscale and implement such solutions on a wider scale, both in Europe and beyond.

Communities of Practice (CoPs), focusing on social learning and stakeholder involvement, have been established in relation to the demonstration cases, to identify and address common, as well as context-specific opportunities and barriers. Based on an initial governance assessment and the CoP experiences so far, we outline the following key learnings.

Learning 1: Address local needs and opportunities

Local synergies are one of the success factors for industrial symbiosis. While geographical proximity has been emphasized the most, synergistic opportunities linked to the availability of natural resources and pre-existing infrastructure are crucial. Already established industrial networks is an important enabler, and lack thereof can be a challenge. Moreover, alignment with regional development agendas and ability to link the solutions to multiple societal challenges (issue-linking) is key to build social acceptance and gain support for water-smart innovations.

Policies and regulations tend to privilege some circularities more than others, e.g., resources recovered from wastewater are given low priority in the EU Circular Economy Action Plan. Public attention can likewise favour some challenges and solutions, whereas other opportunities remain unexplored.

Moreover, the individual challenges that specific water-smart solutions face vary across localities. Therefore:

- ✓ Policymaking may pay more attention to multi-level interactions and varying conditions at the regional and local levels.
- ✓ Policy implementation should be harmonized across regions, but allow a certain degree of flexibility, to enable water-smart symbioses in different local contexts.
- ✓ For water managers, holistic assessment of local needs and opportunities is recommended before selecting circular economy (CE) strategies.

IVAR is a water and waste management company in Southwestern Norway, where there is intensive livestock farming and a surplus of phosphorus. Biogas production was established early, for management of sludge and organic waste and due to close relations with the energy company Lyse, which can inject, and use upgraded biogas through the regional gas grid. The digested sludge forms the basis for a pelletized fertiliser, marketed by Grønn Vekst². Although the area is not sensitive under the Urban Wastewater Directive, biological phosphorus removal has been implemented. In collaboration with key actors in agriculture and the food industry, a new biogas plant substituting 65 000 tons CO₂-e from fossil fuel annually is planned by 2025. Struvite extraction is explored to improve the process as well as the fertilisers. However, prolonged negotiations over the regulation and requirements for bio-based fertilisers cause uncertainty affecting the acceptability and market uptake of the products.

IVAR biogas facility at Grødalaland. Photo: Norconsult.

Field fertilised by Minorga, produced at IVAR for Grønn Vekst. Photo: Dag Idar Jøsang,.

In Accra, Sewerage Systems Ghana Ltd and the Council for Scientific and Industrial Research are demonstrating reuse of treated wastewater for urban agriculture and biochar to replace charcoal made from tropical wood. Social acceptance for anything associated with wastewater is limited. However, the potential for improving urban livelihoods, greening local SMEs, and limiting the reduction of biodiverse rainforest areas is generating increasing interest in water-smart circular economy.

² <https://www.gronnvekst.no/minorga-vekst>

Shallow reservoir and storage, water reuse demo in Accra. Photo: Gordon Akon-Yamga..

Urban agriculture fields where reuse of treated wastewater may bring huge benefits. Photo: Gordon Akon-Yamga.

Learning 2: Need for learning and interaction

Water-smart solutions and circular economy challenge the status quo in the water sector. There is the need for new know-how concerning technologies, business models and supply chain management, strategic planning, and investments, as well as changing policies, standards, and regulations. This highlights the importance of learning; within utilities, between utilities and across to relevant authorities and stakeholder organizations. Collaborative learning between individuals and institutions with different positions and perspectives is important for sense-making as well as the development and adoption of new operation models. However, the water sector tends to be conservative. In some countries it is also fragmented, with small units and limited degree of coordination. Therefore:

- ✓ Beyond improving the efficiency of existing processes and systems, authorities and water utilities need to reflect upon their underlying assumptions, values, and goals in water management to allow a transition towards more water-smart operational modes.
- ✓ In both cases, national water associations and other intermediaries have a crucial role to play.
- ✓ Experiments giving room for action learning and reflection on the required comprehensiveness of change can be fruitful.

In the Netherlands, the Energy and Resources Factory (ERF) is a collaborative venture between the country's 21 Regional Water Authorities. ERF comprises an overarching platform where knowledge and skills with respect to the recovery, processing, and distribution are brought together and shared,

and employees are empowered to try out innovative ideas and unorthodox working methods.³ The collaboration is one of the reasons why the Dutch have reached far in creating a circular economy around water.

In the Czech Republic, the Community of Practice linked to WIDER UPTAKE has addressed the regulatory changes needed to enable reuse of treated wastewater for urban green infrastructure, with a special focus on underlying health and safety concerns. Experimental plant boxes and co-development of a database of water-smart technology solutions, quality standards for different types of resource reuse applications, and user experiences are key elements aiding validation and future uptake of the solutions.

*CoP meeting in Prague, May 2022.
Photo: Herman Helness.*

*Flower in experimental plant box.
Photo: Jiri Wanner.*

Learning 3: Need to align and collaborate across sectors

Circular economy based on water resources requires a balance of costs, risks, and benefits across the actors and stakeholders involved. To realise the potential for value creation there is the need to break down "silos". A narrow focus on sector-specific targets and risks is not conducive. It is necessary to deal actively and constructively with the differing, sometimes conflicting, interests and concerns of different sectors. To do so requires a system perspective and integrated management approach.

There are recent and ongoing revisions of key legislation, both in the EU and at the national level. However, some of these processes drag out in time, due to different sector perspectives and requirements. In several countries, reuse of treated wastewater does not yet exist as a legal category. For some resources from water, lack of end-of-waste criteria hinders market development. Moreover, there are operational barriers, e.g., in terms of permitting procedures and financing of solutions that do not fall within the cost recovery schemes applying in many countries. Therefore:

- ✓ Policymaking must pay more attention to value chains and interactions across sectors.

³ <https://www.efgf.nl/english>

- ✓ Policy implementation should consider thresholds, processes and targets that enable circularity, for example when specifying local limitations for discharge into the sewage system and conditions for reuse of different water-based resources.
- ✓ Water managers may well interact more with potential users in different sectors, to get a better understanding of their practices, needs and preferences.

AquaMinerals was founded as a Shared Service Centre by the Dutch drinking water companies, to achieve economies of scale in marketing residuals from their production processes.⁴ Currently the organisation also serves the Regional Water Authorities, with a focus on circular reuse of materials in the water chain, as well as supply into other circular chains. It works hand in hand with researchers and developers, thus linking supply and demand and contributing to the development of innovative, sustainable value chains. Creation and support for such intermediaries are important to enable circular economy.

In Sicily (Italy), a facility for reuse of treated wastewater has been established in Corleone. There have been initial operation problems, as for many years hydraulic infrastructures have not been in operation because of organizational issues. Also, while the EU Regulation on minimum requirements for water reuse, entering into force in 2023, sets specific quality, monitoring and risk management requirements, a lack of coherence between various pieces of legislation is observed. The interaction between the core actors and relevant policy- and decision-makers is limited. Still, the greatest barriers currently are organizational issues (e.g., appointment of operators of water reuse systems including the establishment of a tariff to be paid by the local farmers) and limited acceptance by other actors, e.g., local farmers and industries.

Corleone wastewater treatment plant. Photo: Giorgio Mannina.

Deviation line for PHA production, Marineo. Photo: Giorgio Mannina.

Learning 4: Change of mindset in water utilities

Considering the opportunities for reuse and resource recovery, it has been argued that future treatment plants should be designed as a form of biorefineries or water resource recovery facilities (WRRFs). This requires a shift from the established linear form of management, focused on safe water cycle services

⁴ <https://aquaminerals.com/home/>

and technical efficiency, towards a circular economy perspective, where the water utility is also a value chain actor providing resources for multiple sectors. This implies a stronger focus on value creation and need for new capabilities, in terms organizational culture and management, agility, innovation, and connectivity with users/customers. In turn, this may have implications for how water utilities should be governed, e.g., in terms of size, ownership and collaboration across regions. Therefore:

- ✓ Policy aiming to support transition towards a water-smart society must consider the need for structural and organizational development, as well as implementation of new technologies.
- ✓ Water managers should work consciously to include new perspectives in strategic planning and recruitment.
- ✓ Incentives and visions to provide direction are crucial to enable new roles and identities.

In the Netherlands, the Association of Netherlands Municipalities and the Association of Regional Water Authorities have a well-established common vision for wastewater management towards 2030. The emphasis is on an integrated, coordinated approach. Wastewater treatment plants are seen as resource recovery facilities, with focus on recovery of at least five resources from municipal wastewater: cellulose, bioplastics, phosphate, alginate-like exopolymers (bio-ALE), and biomass.⁵ This mirrors the overall ambition for a waste free Dutch economy by 2050, reaching a 50% reduction by 2030, and the Dutch Circular Economy strategy, of 2016.

Wastewater Treatment Plant Amsterdam West (Waternet) is treating the waste water of more than 1 million inhabitants, providing 13 million cubic meter of biogas yearly and engaging heavily in nutrient recovery and reuse technologies.⁶ Photo: Waternet.

⁵ https://vng.nl/files/vng/nieuws_attachments/2013/2013115-water-management-2030.pdf

⁶ <https://systemicproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/07/fact-sheet-Waternet-pending.pdf>

Anders Øfsti explaining the patented Bio-P solution of HIAS How2O. Photo: Sigrid Damman.

Innovative peat-free soil products produced by Sirkula in collaboration with HIAS. Photo: Sirkula.

The Norwegian water utility HIAS has a stated ambition to become a water resource recovery facility (WRRF). It has been a frontrunner in technology development and works to become a national competence centre for water-smart solutions. However, the sector as a whole is considered as conservative. Financing is based on full cost recovery, and there are few incentives for implementing radical solutions.

Learning 5: Facilitate innovation

To realise the vision of a water-smart society, there is the need for more innovation in the water sector. It is, therefore, necessary to develop and utilise structures and organizations that can facilitate innovation and entrepreneurship. While decentralised solutions are called for in some cases, more regional coordination and utilities with more institutional capacity are two factors that could be conducive. Financial structures allowing water utilities to work actively with innovation on a continuous basis are important. Furthermore, new intermediaries dedicated to circular economy and/or active facilitation by national and regional authorities and sector associations are crucial.

Currently, economic cost-benefit remains the main focus. However, public actors can accelerate the uptake of water-smart innovations via green public procurement and innovation partnering contracts, where e.g., water utilities and their owners can push technology providers to meet new requirements. Criteria and indicators associated with the EU Taxonomy for sustainable investments may spur the use of such instruments. As at now, setting up tenders for entirely new value chains with several essential parties as required by the Tender Directive is difficult. On the other hand, mutual agreements to create a temporary monopoly for the investing actors is not permitted, under EU Competition Law. Therefore:

- ✓ Policymaking must address the need to create a stronger focus on innovation and co-creation for change towards water smartness in water utilities.

- ✓ Green public procurement and innovation partnering should be applied more consistently, to stimulate the development and uptake of symbiotic water-smart solutions.
- ✓ Creating a space or "playground" where chain actors can realise a non-existing chain should be considered, to enable circular value chains based on water resources.

In the Netherlands, the system of water taxes allows Waternet and other regional water authorities to dedicate own funds to innovation and collaborate widely to facilitate advanced circular economy solutions, including applications for recovered raw materials such as the production of innovative biocomposite materials by NPSP.

Example use of NPSP biocomposite; "3D Facade Panels", Studio Marco Vermeulen, Client ProRail.

Zoya Zarafshani presenting at the lab of NPSP. Photo: Herman Helness.

In Norway, a system of full cost recovery via user fees and use of "best available technologies" gives less room for this. However, there are slight variations in practice, and water utilities such as HIAS and IVAR have established joint ventures and subsidiaries for development and upscaling of their innovative technologies and products.

The technology providers in WIDER UPTAKE have mixed experiences with sustainability requirements in public procurement. In some cases, innovation partnering was both exciting and fruitful. However, the competence and experience among utilities and consultants is variable. In some cases, the consultant's preferences could be guessed in advance. One technology provider found that while the R&D department of the water utility was actively engaged in co-developing water-smart solutions, the procurement office did not include sustainability criteria. Another noted that although sustainability criteria are defined, they are not weighted equally to price.

This brief was written by Sigrid Damman, Henrik Brynthe Lund, Tuukka Mäkitie, and Herman Helness, and designed by Bjørnar Nørstebø (all from SINTEF). For more information and updates on the activities in WIDER UPTAKE, please visit the project website: <https://www.wider-uptake.eu>